

NEXUS BETWEEN TRADE OPENNESS, URBANISATION, INDUSTRIALISATION AND CO₂ EMISSIONS: EVIDENCE FROM BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Trade openness and urbanisation are supposed to be driving forces for economic growth. However, unplanned and fast urban growth coupled with lax trade restrictions can cause serious problems, impairing economic stability and environmental quality. The purpose of this study is to determine how industrialisation, trade openness and urbanisation have affected CO₂ emissions in Bangladesh. Bangladesh's economy, recognised as one of the fastest-growing in South Asia, has particular difficulties because of its susceptibility to natural calamities. The analysis employs yearly data from the World Development Indicators, spanning from 1972 to 2022, utilising the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to explore these effects. The findings of the study indicate that urbanisation and trade openness are exerting negative pressure on the environment in the long run. These findings have implications for policymakers to formulate policies focusing on planned urbanisation and trade strategies that safeguard the environment while fostering economic development.

Keywords: Trade openness, Urbanisation, Industrialisation, ARDL, CO₂emissions,

1. Introduction

Over the last century, the exceptional global economic expansion has taken place. This expansion has increased economic growth, urbanisation, industrialisation, and economic integration, especially in emerging

economies. These interrelated forces have played an essential role in transforming economies, raising living standards, and shaping modern societies. However, these developments are coming at the cost of environmental challenges. The world is grappling with worsening environmental degradation and climate change, seriously threatening people's lives everywhere (Abbasi et al., 2020; Li & Zhou, 2019). The atmospheric concentration of greenhouse gases (GHGs) is increasing, with carbon dioxide (CO₂) being the primary contributor to climate change (Parveen et al., 2023). Emissions of CO₂ have drastically increased, especially since industrialisation. Industrialisation contributes to both environmental degradation and economic prosperity. On the one hand, greater productivity and urbanisation significantly increase GDP and improve material well-being (Hossain et al., 2024; Samuel et al., 2024a). On the other hand, this expansion frequently results in pollution and resource depletion, among other adverse environmental effects (Huang 1, 2024; Samuel et al., 2024b).

Urbanisation is another factor closely related to environmental degradation (Odugbesan & Rjoub, 2020). The World Bank estimates that 57.25% of the world's population lives in cities in 2023. According to UN projections, this percentage will increase to about 68% by 2050, indicating a persistent urbanisation trend. This expansion is anticipated to be driven mainly by Asia and Africa, where urban populations are predicted to double between 2000 and 2030 (R. Ali et al., 2019). Urbanisation is the process of moving from rural to urban regions for better opportunities and living conditions. Access to improved education, regular work, and improved facilities, including social services, infrastructure, and healthcare, are frequently the driving forces behind this movement. This movement disrupts the infrastructure and causes environmental issues in cities. Urban economic activities significantly affect the environment. Dense populations in cities can overwhelm the environment's ability to handle waste and pollution while also shaping how resources are consumed, often increasing pressure on local ecosystems (Dutta & Hazarika, 2023).

Economic integration is widely regarded as a crucial trend and a powerful tool that nations can utilize to foster economic growth and eradicate poverty. Many developing countries have changed trade policies during the last few decades to promote greater openness to global commerce.

This strategic approach is built on the notion that more involvement in the global trade network may promote industrial development, economic growth, and improved living standards. To improve access to commodities, technology, and investment, these nations want to further integrate into the global economy by reducing trade barriers and promoting cross-border business. Ultimately, these actions are viewed as raising people's quality of life and encouraging sustainable development (Van Tran, 2020). Trade expansion can help spread clean technology and boost the economy, but it can also worsen environmental damage by moving polluting industries to countries with laxer environmental laws. In developed countries, trade openness tends to reduce pollution, while in developing countries, it often leads to higher emissions, aligning with the Pollution Haven Hypothesis (PHH) (Taşdemir, 2022).

This study aims to comprehend the variables driving CO₂ emissions in Bangladesh. Bangladesh, characterised by its swiftly growing economy and significant susceptibility to environmental degradation, is a crucial case for examining this relationship. Bangladesh is the eighth country in the world in terms of population and the twelfth most densely populated. Presently, Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh, is the 11th largest megacity globally and is anticipated to become the sixth largest megacity by 2030, with a population of 27.37 million. The nation has experienced notable structural changes since the liberalisation policies of the 1990s, characterised by a surge in foreign direct investment, the emergence of export-driven sectors such as textiles, and enhanced economic integration. Bangladesh has emerged as the second-largest exporter of textiles and clothing. This export-led approach has had a remarkable effect on Bangladesh's open trade.

Although these transformations have propelled GDP growth and alleviated poverty, they have simultaneously placed pressure on the nation's natural resources, leading to air and water pollution, land degradation, and increased vulnerability to climate change.

Bangladesh is witnessing rapid economic growth; it has emerged as South Asia's second most rapidly growing economy and ranks fifth in economic growth on a global scale (WDI 2022).

Bangladesh has consistently achieved an annual GDP growth rate of 6-7% for the past thirty years.

However, this development is accompanied by a rising population and mounting environmental challenges, presenting a complex balance between progress and sustainability. As per the (WDI 2022), per capita CO₂ emissions in Bangladesh have marked a significant growth. It rose to 0.53 metric tons in 2016 from 0.20 in 1996. It has an 8.25% yearly growth rate. Therefore, this study will help explore the underlying factors behind increased emissions in Bangladesh. It will also help formulate policies that are favourable for sustainable development.

This is how the rest of the article is organised: the following part has a thorough literature review. The data and methodology applied in this study are detailed in section 3. In section 4, the focus shifts to the presentation of the analysis and empirical findings, whereas section 5 concludes the research and presents implications for policy.

2. Review of existing literature

The relationship between economic activity and environmental sustainability has drawn attention from researchers, particularly the impact of urbanisation, industrialisation, and trade openness on CO₂ emissions. Understanding these dynamics is essential for developing effective environmental policy as nations strive to increase their economies. This literature review compiles research on the relationship between these three parameters and CO₂ emissions.

Trade Openness and CO₂ Emissions

A study by Karedla et al. (2021) examined the connections among India's economic growth, trade openness, manufacturing, and CO₂ emissions from 1971 to 2016. The findings indicate that the rise in manufacturing and economic growth has increased CO₂ emissions, whereas trade openness is negatively correlated with CO₂ emissions. Shahbaz et al. (2017) further validated the negative association between trade openness and pollution in their analysis of a panel comprising 105 countries across high, middle, and low-income categories.

Conversely, a study by Van Tran (2020) examined sixty-six developing economies from 1971 to 2017 and unveiled a positive correlation between trade openness and CO₂ emissions. Goswami et al. (2023), in their study on India from 1980 to 2021, reported that trade openness leads to increased CO₂ emissions. In Malaysia's case, Nurgazina et al. (2021)

confirm that trade openness contributes to CO₂ emissions. In contrast, a study by Kllavuz and Doğan (2021) for Turkey covering the years 1961-2018 indicates that trade openness does not influence CO₂ emissions. Nonetheless, certain studies indicate that income influences the relationship between trade and the environment. For instance, research conducted by Le et al. (2016) involving a panel of ninety-eight countries revealed that trade tends to benefit the environment in developed nations, whereas it adversely affects developing nations. Similarly, the outcomes of the study by Wang and Zhang (2021) indicate that trade openness has benefited high-income countries by leading to cutbacks in carbon emissions. In contrast, it proved unfavourable for low-income countries by increasing carbon emissions.

Urbanisation and CO₂ Emissions

Research by Abbasi et al. (2020) using a panel of eight Asian nations, including Bangladesh, demonstrates a positive and substantial correlation between urbanisation and CO₂ emissions. Pata (2018) noted that urbanisation exacerbates CO₂ emissions in Turkey. Likewise, analysis undertaken by Ahmad et al. (2021), R. Ali et al. (2019), Anwar et al. (2020), Dutta and Hazarika (2023), Goswami et al. (2023), Nurgazina et al. (2021), Parveen et al. (2023), and Wu et al. (2022) indicate that urbanisation exacerbates CO₂ emissions across all examined samples. Mahmood et al. (2020) also saw comparable findings in Saudi Arabia. Contradictory results were shown by H. S. Ali et al. (2017), Asif et al. (2020), D. Li et al. (2024), and Saidi and Mbarek (2017), who demonstrated an inverse correlation between urbanisation and carbon emissions. Conversely, studies done by AFRIYIE et al. (2022) as well as Bosah et al. (2021) indicated that urbanisation has no significant environmental impact.

Industrialisation and CO₂ Emissions

The study by Rehman et al. (2021) on Pakistan indicated that industrialisation positively affects CO₂ emissions. Likewise, research conducted by Biswas et al. (2024), Rahman et al. (2024), and Raihan et al. (2024) in the context of Bangladesh indicated a positive correlation between industrialisation and emissions. The textile and ready-made garment sectors significantly contribute to emissions, representing 67.8% of the total, mainly due to onsite fuel combustion (Biswas et al., 2024).

The study by Borsha et al. (2024) identified a significant negative link between CO₂ emissions and the utilisation of renewable energy in Bangladesh, suggesting that sustainable practices can mitigate the adverse effects of development. Likewise, Haider et al. (2024) and Patel and Mehta (2023) indicated that long-term industrialisation enhances the environment by adopting cleaner practices. However, research such as (Idowu et al., 2023; Lin et al., 2015) indicated no substantial effect of industrialisation on CO₂ emissions.

3. Data and Methodology

The data regarding all the variables were obtained from World Development Indicators (WDI) to analyse the causal connection between CO₂ emissions, trade openness, urbanisation, and industrialisation. The dataset spans from 1972 to 2022. The chosen time period is determined by the readily available data. Table 1 provides the sources and depiction of the data.

Table 1. Data source and depiction.

Variable	Symbol	Unit of Measurement	Source
CO ₂ Emissions	lnCO ₂	Mt CO ₂ per year	WDI
Industrialisation	lnINV	Industry value added (% of GDP)	WDI
Urbanisation	lnURB	Urban population (% of total population)	WDI
Trade Openness	lnTO	(% of GDP)	WDI

Source: World Development Indicators

This study aimed to examine the potential short and long-run relationships among CO₂ emissions, trade openness, urbanisation, and industrialisation. To achieve the stated objective, this study utilises the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bound Testing approach, a methodology proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001). The ARDL analysis investigates the long-run and short-run relationships among variables in a time series context. Considering that the series in question displays a mixed order of integration and not any of the variables are integrated of order 2, i.e. I(2), applying the ARDL test is feasible and appropriate. The ARDL model can be expressed in standard form through the following equation:

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_i \Delta x_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_i \Delta z_{t-i} + \lambda_1 y_{t-1} + \lambda_2 x_{t-1} + \lambda_3 z_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad (1)$$

In this context, y_t represents the dependent variable. The parameters λ_1 , λ_2 , and λ_3 delineated the long-term relationship, whereas β_i , δ_i , and ε_i signify coefficients related to short-term dynamics. Furthermore, α_0 and μ_t represent the constant and error terms, respectively.

Two key steps are commonly utilised in the ARDL analysis process. To begin, it is necessary to carry out a cointegration study, which involves employing the F-bounds test to evaluate the degree to which the variables are cointegrated. Equation 2 is the representation of both the short-term and the long-term dynamics.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln CO_2 = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta \ln CO_{2t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln INV_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln TO_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln URP_{t-i} + \lambda_1 \ln CO_{2t-1} \\ & + \lambda_2 \ln INV_{t-1} + \lambda_3 \ln TO_{t-1} + \lambda_4 \ln URP_{t-1} + \mu_t \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The model delineates the dependent and independent variables as follows: CO₂ refers to carbon dioxide emissions; INV indicates industrial value added; URP pertains to the urban population; TO signifies trade openness; ln denotes the logarithm; Δ indicates the first difference; α_0 symbolises the constant term; β represents the short-run parameters, while λ denotes the long-run parameters; finally μ_t represents the error term.

The null hypothesis (H_0) posits the absence of cointegration, while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) asserts the presence of cointegration.

$$(H_0) : \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \dots \beta_k = 0$$

$$(H_1) : \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \dots \beta_k \neq 0$$

The subsequent phase of ARDL analysis incorporates the Error Correction Model (ECM), utilising the least squares method to assess the adjustment rate towards long-term equilibrium. This model evaluates the sensitivity of the dependent variable to variations from the equilibrium relationship.

It measures the rate at which the system rectifies short-term perturbations and specifies the size and direction of this adjustment. Furthermore, the ECM enables the discernment of the short-term impacts of independent variables on the dependent variable. The overarching model of ECM is articulated in equation (3).

$$\Delta \ln CO_2 = \alpha_0 + \sum_{t-1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta \ln CO_{2t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta \ln INV_{t-1} + \sum_{t-1}^n \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln TO_{t-i} + \sum_{t-1}^n \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln URP_{t-i} + \delta ECM_{t-1} + \mu_t \tag{3}$$

In this context, ECM_{-1} signifies the error correction term, δ represents the adjustment rate after a short-term shock, and all coefficients illustrate the short-term dynamics related to convergence to equilibrium.

Before conducting ARDL analysis, assessing the stationarity of the time series variables is essential. ARDL, similar to numerous econometric models, depends on the assumption of stationarity; any violation of this assumption may result in spurious regression outcomes and unreliable inferences. In the context of ARDL, the series must exhibit a mixed order of integration, i.e. ARDL models can handle variables that are stationary at level I(0) or stationary at first difference I(1).

4. Empirical Findings and Analysis

4.1 Descriptive Statistics and Correlations

This segment presented descriptive data and a correlation matrix before investigating the nexus among the variables.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	lnCO ₂	lnINV	lnNTO	lnURP
Mean	3.087986	3.052563	3.244408	3.055223
Median	3.107756	3.110174	3.269511	3.102352
Maximum	4.700335	3.524007	3.873509	3.681628
Minimum	1.207646	1.802386	2.397498	2.066989
Std. Dev.	1.065749	0.332380	0.344268	0.436403

Skewness	-0.035873	-1.626411	0.019366	-0.631503
Kurtosis	1.786547	6.681899	2.367691	2.649251
Jarque-Bera	3.201501	52.29734	0.869516	3.722784
Probability	0.201745	0.000000	0.647421	0.155456
Sum	160.5753	158.7333	168.7092	158.8716
Sum Sq. Dev.	57.92684	5.634293	6.044537	9.712839
Observations	52	52	52	52

Source: Author's Computation

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 outline that trade openness exhibits the maximum mean, then CO₂ emissions, urbanisation, and industrialisation. CO₂ has the highest variance, while industrialisation has a minimum. Table 3 of the correlation matrix demonstrates that all the variables are positively correlated. These correlations present only the possible relation between the variables. This study will further describe these relationships below.

Table 3. Correlation Matrix

	lnCO ₂	lnINV	lnTO	lnURP
lnCO ₂	1.000000	0.857664	0.825584	0.972031
lnINV	0.857664	1.000000	0.620301	0.927258
lnTO	0.825584	0.620301	1.000000	0.778692
lnURP	0.972031	0.927258	0.778692	1.000000

Source: Author's Computation

4.2 Unit Root Analysis

We employ a combination of statistical tests to check whether the series is stationary. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron

(PP) tests are utilised to check unit roots. Moreover, the Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt, and Shin (KPSS) test is used as an auxiliary method to confirm the stationarity of the series. Together, these tests provide a comprehensive assessment of the unit roots. The results of this analysis are provided in Table 4. The unit root test results indicate stationarity at I(0) and I(1), with no variable exhibiting stationarity at I(2).

Table 4: Unit root analysis results

	PP		ADF		KPSS	
	At Level I(0)	At First Difference I(1)	At Level I(0)	At First Difference I(1)	At Level I(0)	At First Difference I(1)
lnCO ₂	-1.5314	-7.7916*	-1.3775	-7.7916*	0.9733*	0.1766
lnINV	-3.3458**	-8.9133	-2.9658**	-9.2221	0.8432*	0.3119
lnTO	-1.5370	-8.5029*	-1.7404	-8.2996*	0.7776*	0.0930
lnURP	-3.6852*	-1.6009	-2.5268	-1.2661	0.9379*	0.4700

Note: * and ** denote 1% and 5% significance levels, respectively.

Source: Author's Computation

4.3 ARDL Bound test

The results of the ARDL bound test shown in Table 5 indicate long-run cointegration, with the calculated F-statistics (15.84009) surpassing the upper bound I(1) critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels.

Table 5: Results of the ARDL Bound test

Null hypothesis: No level relationship				
F-Statistics		10%	5%	1%
15.84009	Lower Bound I(0)	2.37	2.79	3.65
	Upper Bound I(1)	3.2	3.67	4.66

Source: Author's Computation

4.4 Long-run Estimates

The findings of long-run estimates are presented in Table 6. Trade openness (lnTO) and urbanisation (lnURP) are statistically significant

factors affecting environmental quality. The evidence suggests that a 1% rise in trade openness and urbanisation will increase emissions by 0.66% and 1.90%, respectively. These results are in concurrence with the studies conducted by Lalon et al. (2023), Murshed and Yusuf Saadat (2018), and Raihan et al. (2022). The findings indicate that the economic globalisation and urbanisation experienced in Bangladesh have led to environmental degradation over time. The third variable, industrialisation, in the study, did not demonstrate a significant impact on carbon emissions over the long term.

Table 6. Long-run Estimation

Dependent Variable: $\ln CO_2$				
Independent Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistics	p-value
lnINV	0.685340	0.439294	1.560095	0.1286
lnTO	0.668749	0.140798	4.749708	0.0000*
lnURP	1.900068	0.360671	5.268151	0.0000*
C	-6.984259	0.644714	-10.83311	0.0000*

Note: * indicate the significance level at 1%.

Source: Author's Computation

4.5 ECM and short-run estimates

After establishing the long-run relationship, examining the adjustments (error correction model) that lead towards the long-run relationship is necessary. Table 7 illustrates the short-run relationship. Over the long run, industrialisation proves to be of minor importance, whereas in the short run, industrialisation, trade openness, and urbanisation all exert a positive and significant coefficient with CO₂ emissions. With each 1% rise in industrialisation, trade openness, and urbanisation, carbon emissions increase by 0.28%, 0.15%, and 7.52%, respectively. Urbanisation can be observed as a significant factor in the short run. A negative and significant ECM (-1) coefficient at 1% indicates the stability of the long-run cointegration among variables in the ARDL model. It confirms that the model is pertinent for evaluation. The ECM reflects the speed at which deviations from the long-term equilibrium are rectified over time. Therefore, the coefficient of -0.3833 indicates that any shock in the CO₂

emissions will be adjusted to the equilibrium in the long run by a 38% rate.

Table 7. ECM and short-run estimates

Dependent Variable: LnCO₂				
Independent Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistics	p-value
$\Delta(\ln INV)$	0.287604	0.126030	2.282033	0.0293**
$\Delta(\ln INV(-1))$	-0.145909	0.106894	-1.364984	0.1818
$\Delta(\ln INV(-2))$	0.330352	0.078678	4.198802	0.0002*
$\Delta(\ln TO)$	0.156776	0.043666	3.590336	0.0011*
$\Delta(\ln TO(-1))$	-0.208827	0.046026	-4.537135	0.0001*
$\Delta(\ln TO(-2))$	-0.082819	0.041752	-1.983587	0.0559**
$\Delta(\ln TO(-3))$	-0.097473	0.042410	-2.298356	0.0282**
$\Delta(\ln URP)$	7.525618	0.908317	8.285231	0.0000*
$\Delta(\ln URP(-1))$	-7.535815	1.497228	-5.033179	0.0000*
$\Delta(\ln URP(-2))$	7.390943	1.491977	4.953792	0.0000*
$\Delta(\ln URP(-3))$	-6.016425	0.945570	-6.362751	0.0000*
CointEq(-1)*	-0.383325	0.040609	-9.439308	0.0000*

Note: * and ** denote 1% and 5% significance levels, respectively.

Source: Author's Computation

4.6 Diagnostics and Stability Test

Diagnostic measures are utilised to evaluate the stability of the model. Table 7 reports the findings of these tests. The analysis reveals no autocorrelation in the model, as indicated by the Breusch-Godfrey LM test, and no signs of heteroscedasticity, as evaluated by the Breusch-Pagan test. The Jarque-Bera test validated the model's normality. The suitability of the model's functional form is validated by the Ramsey RESET test. To evaluate the stability of model parameters over time, we used the cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMSQ) and the cumulative sum (CUSUM). As the blue line lies within the confidence interval of 5%, the stability of the model parameters can be justified. Figure 1 presents the plots of CUSUM, and Figure 2 presents CUSUMSQ.

Table 7. Diagnostic tests

Tests	Statistics	<i>p</i> -value
Normality	0.985624	0.610906
Serial correlation	0.517437	0.6013
Heteroscedasticity	0.587791	0.8625
Ramsey RESET test	0.176017	0.8614

Source: Author's Computation

Figure 1. CUSUM graphs.

Figure 2. CUSUM (sq) graphs.

5. Conclusion and Policy Implications

Using annual data spanning from 1970 to 2022 for Bangladesh, this study examines the nexus between industrialisation, trade openness, urbanisation, and CO₂ emissions. After verifying the order of integration of variables and getting a combination of I(0) and I(1), the ARDL bound test methodology is employed. The findings from the ARDL test indicate that urbanisation and trade openness significantly contribute to an increase in CO₂ emissions over the long term. According to the findings, the environmental quality of Bangladesh is facing a threat as a result of the rapid urbanisation and economic globalisation that is taking place in the country.

The results of this study present several policy implications. Urbanisation adversely affects environmental health due to unregulated urban expansion in many developing nations. As nations develop, a significant portion of the population migrates to urban centres for improved living conditions, employment opportunities, education, and various amenities. The increase in urban population exerts pressure on the local environment and escalates the demand for energy consumption across multiple applications. Therefore, well-structured urbanisation should be promoted, and strategies to augment income in rural regions should be prioritised.

Practices like vertical gardening, solar energy installation and switching to renewable energy sources in already-settled cities could help mitigate emissions. Secondly, trade liberalisation contributes to heightened CO₂ emissions, as the expansion of trade stimulates economic activity within a country, thereby elevating production levels. This escalation in production subsequently amplifies energy demand across various sectors of the economy. Concurrently, it facilitates the relocation of polluting industries and enterprises from developed nations to developing countries. This is primarily attributable to inadequate environmental protection and legislation prioritising economic growth over ecological considerations. Consequently, policymakers must establish stringent regulations to protect the environment and explore renewable energy solutions to meet energy demands.

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